

Article

How Much Is Needed? Discussion on Benchmarks for Primary Energy Input and Global Warming Potential Caused by Building Construction

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Abstract: The operational energy efficiency of new buildings in the EU should be at the level of ultra-low or near-zero energy buildings. It is therefore relatively difficult to achieve further energy savings. However, the pre-operational phase—raw material sourcing, manufacturing, transportation, and construction—offers significant energy savings and greenhouse gas reduction opportunities, referred to as embodied energy and equivalent CO₂ emissions. Unlike operational energy, no standard or legislative criteria have yet been established for embodied energy. Setting maximum embodied energy values converted to the unit of heated building area, accounting for building shape factor, and differentiating between high-mass and lightweight constructions are proposed. This study illustrates assessing environmental indicators based on building shape, highlighting the necessity of relative assessments over absolute values to favour energy efficiency. It also emphasizes that precise criteria should derive from authentic data collected during the energy certification and building permitting processes. Integrating assessments of embodied energy and operational energy demand facilitates a comprehensive evaluation of buildings’ environmental performance.

Keywords: primary energy input; global warming potential; embodied energy; environmental assessment; buildings; energy certification

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1. Introduction

This article is written from the perspective of Central European realities. It is evident that the European Union, as represented by the European Commission and the European Parliament, has a vested interest in addressing the climate crisis and reducing energy dependence on fossil fuels. This intention is also evident in the European Union’s Green

Deal programme [1], the objectives of which are notably ambitious. They demonstrate not only a desire to address environmental issues but also to assume a leading role in this domain, setting significant challenges and generally providing a positive example for the rest of the world. Nevertheless, the overarching objective is to safeguard and enhance the quality of life in Europe, which represents its fundamental appeal [2].

A substantial corpus of literature exists on the potential of the construction sector to reduce energy consumption and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions through the reduction of fossil fuel combustion. In order to realise this potential, the European Union has also set an unprecedented example in terms of the enforcement of regulations on the energy efficiency of buildings [3–7] through the continuous improvement of standard calculation tools [8,9].

These legislative and standardisation measures focus almost exclusively on the operational period of the overall life cycle of buildings. Their implementation has been so effective that currently only new-build projects at the level of ultra-low or near-zero energy buildings are approved in EU Member States. As a result, further reductions in operational energy demand are very difficult to achieve. This presents a challenge to the potential for reducing the summer overheating of buildings or incorporating renewable energy sources more efficiently.

In addition to the operational period of the building life cycle, the period preceding the building's commissioning, encompassing the stages from raw material sourcing through product manufacturing, transportation to the construction site, assembly, and final construction, presents a significant opportunity for energy savings and greenhouse gas reduction. This period can be characterised in terms of embodied, grey, or embedded energy, as well as the resulting GHG emissions. The notions of embodied, grey, or embedded energy are used to describe the same characteristic, namely, the overall energy intensity of the building construction. However, these notions are not entirely stable. Henceforth, the term "embodied energy" is employed for the sole purpose of this discussion. The greenhouse gas emissions resulting from the construction of a building are referred to as the equivalent CO₂ emissions due to embodied energy. The equivalent CO₂ emissions are a kind of proxy indicator of greenhouse gas emissions [10].

In contrast to operational energy or the equivalent CO₂ emissions resulting from the operation of the building, there are no legislative restrictions on embodied energy or the greenhouse gas emissions associated with it. It is evident that there is a lack of legislative restrictions and uniform criteria or standard calculation procedures for setting maximum permissible values, even when voluntary sustainability assessment schemes such as the British Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method (BREEAM) [11], the US Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED) [12], the Deutsche Gesellschaft für Nachhaltiges Bauen (DGNB) (German Sustainable Building Council) method [13], etc., are excluded from consideration. These schemes list primary energy input (PEI) and global warming potential (GWP) due to building construction as one of the categories and provide corresponding benchmarks, although the benchmarks themselves are not entirely clear and the weights assigned to them in the overall sustainability assessment vary. The introduction of the so-called Environmental Product Declaration for Buildings (EPDB), which should also include these values, represents an initiative to address this issue. However, there is no mention of maximum permissible values in this context either. The idea of the EPDB is based on the system of Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) [14], which is, in the European Union, driven by the Construction Products Regulation (CPR) [15]. The 2018 JRC Technical Report of the European Commission [16] introduces a concept for the assessment of the environmental performance of buildings based on benchmarking the building design against standard and/or best practices. In order to develop such benchmarks, a graduated approach is foreseen, starting on a simple basis

and being refined and increasing in complexity over time, as data collection on buildings and relative processes become more complete and precise [16]. Nevertheless, this approach assumes a broad survey of the building stock. The disadvantage of this solution is that, in the first step, it is necessary to obtain a representative sample based on a large amount of data, which means that a large number of buildings will have to be counted and evaluated by the relevant public authorities or their delegated organisations. This procedure is both financially expensive and time-consuming.

The second option, as outlined in this study, involves the transfer of data generation to the building community in the preparation of the building permit application, analogous to the energy certification process. This approach is comprised of two phases. In the initial phase, the transitional phase (one to two years), building permit applicants would be required to supply PEI and GWP values calculated on the basis of a uniform methodology (to be determined). These values would not yet be subject to assessment, as no benchmark values would be available at this stage.

Once the national authorities concerned deemed themselves to have sufficient data, they would proceed to the second stage. In the second phase, the relevant national authorities would establish appropriate benchmarks according to the objectives and ambitions of the country. These would already have to be met by building permit applications and energy assessment within the energy certification process, and it would be possible, and necessary, to refine the criteria over time.

This approach offers several advantages over benchmarking against environmental indicator values based on an assessment of existing building stock:

- The approach can be implemented relatively quickly, as there is no need to wait for a survey of the existing building stock;
- The values obtained will provide a more accurate representation of the embodied energy levels in new buildings than the values derived from an existing building stock survey, which, by its nature, will have to be based on estimates;
- The data will not be gathered from a single source, but rather from the entire community of builders.

Once a representative amount of data is available, questions of criteria development arise. The first natural consideration is to set a maximum value as a single fixed number, e.g., PEI/m² or GWP/m² of heated/cooled building area, depending, for example, on the type of building, e.g., separately for single-family houses, separately for apartment buildings, separately for office buildings, and so on. However, such an approach does not take into account the shape of the building. This can be taken into account by relating the embodied energy to the so-called building shape factor, and the criteria can also be graded.

The present study, based on a hypothetical and very simplified building, briefly describes how such a procedure could look like and what the trend of results would be for its different shapes. The idea of relating embodied energy and equivalent CO₂ emissions to the shape of the building and its simplified demonstration represents the key point of this study, which aims to contribute to the ongoing debate on the identification and refinement of benchmarks for the assessment and limitation of primary energy non-renewable total (PENRT) and GWP. The concept of the relationship between building geometry and the amount of embodied energy is analogous to the assessment of the heating/cooling energy demand of buildings, which is a standard procedure in the context of building energy certification.

In the late 1980s and early 1990s, researchers such as Mahdavi [17], Heindl [18], Uyttenbroeck [19], and Panzhauser [20] attempted to develop standards for evaluating the overall heat transfer coefficient (U-value) of buildings. In general, the U-value represents the thermal transmittance of a given structure (fragment/composite), defining the magnitude

of the heat flux through an area of 1 m^2 of the structure perpendicular to the heat flux at a temperature difference of 1 Kelvin. The efforts of these scientists resulted in the so-called Lines of European U-values (originally K-values) scheme, which allows the assessment of the average heat transfer coefficient of a building as a function of the building's shape factor. This scheme later became the basis for assessing heating demand. Although the assessment of the average U-value and heat demand based on the shape factor is standardised in most EU Member States, current legislation in most countries, including Germany, does not prescribe such an assessment and only requires that a maximum allowable value, set according to the type of building, is not exceeded. In Slovakia, for example, new single-family houses should have a heating demand of no more than $43 \text{ kWh}/(\text{m}^2\text{K})$. The reason for this approach is probably the fact that assessing the heating/cooling needs of buildings has become a very complex matter, taking into account solar gains, building equipment and occupancy, ventilation losses, but also compliance with hygiene criteria. However, in the case of environmental indicators, the basic functionality of building structures in terms of thermal and operational energy is usually assumed [21] and not addressed. Consequently, the evaluation of environmental indicators in relation to the shape factor should be considerably more straightforward. The issue pertains exclusively to the environmental quality of the products and materials utilized, as well as their quantity. The objective of this study is, therefore, as follows:

- to demonstrate, by means of a simple example, the method and importance of assessing environmental indicators on the basis of the shape factor;
- to show that the assessment of buildings on the basis of absolute values makes little sense as it favours smaller buildings and has little predictive value in terms of energy efficiency. It is, therefore, more appropriate to assess environmental indicators per unit of floor area of the heated space of the building;
- to point out that a distinction should be made between high-mass and lightweight construction and, therefore, that the criteria should not be set so much according to the type of building in terms of its function, i.e., apartment block, office building, etc., but rather according to its mass, at least for both basic types—lightweight and high-mass construction.

The establishment of precise criteria should be grounded in authentic data concerning environmental indicators, such as the amount of embodied energy and equivalent CO_2 emissions. As previously highlighted, the most suitable approach to acquiring these data would be through the energy certification and building permitting process. The calculation of embodied energy and equivalent CO_2 emissions can easily be linked to the calculation of the energy required for building operation, in this case for heating and cooling, with the same input geometric data in both cases, thus simplifying the calculation. Moreover, the integration of the assessment of the embodied PENRT and GWP with the evaluation of building operational energy demand provides a clear and accessible framework for understanding the intrinsic link between these components in assessing the environmental performance of buildings.

2. Materials and Methods

From the point of view of the building operation, in terms of heat demand for its heating and cooling, the determining factors are mainly the building geometry and the material and technological quality of the envelope enclosing the heated/cooled indoor environment. The geometry of the building is mostly defined by the ratio of the heat exchange surface of the envelope to the volume of the heated/cooled space (in Austria, for example, the ratio is the opposite, i.e., the volume of the heated/cooled space to the heat exchange surface of the building envelope [20]). The material-technological quality,

for the purpose of this study, is characterized by the PENRT, GWP, and U-values of the most important fragments of the envelope (wall, roof, floor, windows and doors). The determination of the U-values of the envelope fragments surrounding the heated/cooled space serves as the foundation for calculating the heat demand for its heating/cooling. As the focus of this study is primarily on the context of Central Europe, where cooling demand is not a significant factor, and given the specificities of calculating cooling demand, which is performed separately from heating demand, in the following sections, only the heating demand is referred to in the context of building operation.

2.1. Shape Factor

The idea of associating the operational energy rating of buildings with their geometry (A/V) dates back to the 1980s [17–20], with attempts to limit it fairly in the sense that more compact buildings could afford higher heat losses than less compact buildings while still being classified within the same category. Initially, the focus was on the average U-value of the building envelope in relation to the building geometry; however, later, it was the heat demand for heating and, finally, the primary energy demand for building operation. The latter method of assessment only came about in the second decade of this century. The chart in Figure 1 illustrates the correlation between the average U-value of the building envelope (residential buildings) and the shape factor in accordance with the requirements of the Slovak STN 73 0540 of 2012 [22] and the German EnEV 2001 (in German standard and legislation the average U-value of the building envelope is described as H_T —Spezifischer Transmissionswärmeverlust (Specific Transmission Heat Loss), having the same unit as U-value) [23]. The German EnEV presents the U-values before and STN 73 0540 after their tightening due to the European Energy Performance of Buildings Directive 2010 [4]. It should be noted that the maximum and, hence, average U-values have also been lowered in Germany since 2010.

Figure 1. The correlation between the average U-value [W/(m²K)] of the building envelope (residential buildings) and the shape factor [m⁻¹] in accordance with the requirements of the Slovak STN 73 0540 of 2012 and the German EnEV 2001 (in German standard and legislation the average U-value of the building envelope is described as H_T —Spezifischer Transmissionswärmeverlust (Specific Transmission Heat Loss), having the same unit as U-value).

However, the average U-value merely defines the quality of the envelope in terms of thermal protection. The way the building is used, solar gains, the thermal response in terms of heat storage capacity, and heat losses through ventilation are taken into account in the subsequent calculation of the heat demand for heating.

2.2. Aim of the Study

The requirements for the average U-values of the building envelope have become increasingly rigorous over time, reaching values that no longer make economic or environmental sense to reduce further [24,25]. From a design perspective, the only remaining opportunity for reducing energy consumption and GHG emissions is in the area of building fabrication, specifically the reduction in embodied energy and the emissions caused by it. The objective of the present study is to examine the relationship between the PENRT due to embodied energy and the building shape factor, with the aim of contributing to the potential development of criteria that limit the magnitude of the PENRT in building manufacture. This is demonstrated with a simplified example of a building with a high-mass envelope. The study then compares the range of results obtained with those for a building with a lightweight envelope calculated using the same procedure.

2.3. Simplified Example

The present study solely considers the building envelope and is inclusive of the roof and ground floor, as this is similarly employed in the calculation of the building's heating energy demand. The analysis did not consider ceilings and internal walls. This approach is a simplification in an attempt to avoid the inclusion of excessive detail, which could otherwise distract from the objective. Table 1 presents the PENRT and GWP values for the individual components of the high-mass envelope, including the wall, roof, windows, and floor at ground level.

Table 1. The PENRT and GWP values for the individual components of the high-mass building under study. The PENRT and GWP values of each component were calculated for 1 m² as the product of the unit values and the widths considered in the study. In the case of windows, a size of 2 m² was assumed.

Component	Raw Density [kg/m ³]	Unit	Width [m]	Size [m ²]	PENRT/Unit [MJ]	PENRT/Component [MJ]	GWP/Unit [kg CO ₂ -Equivalent]	GWP/Component [kg CO ₂ -Equivalent]
Window (PVC)		m ²		2.00	1583.00	3166	90.57	181.14
Wall:								
Reinforced concrete	2400.00	m ³	0.25		929.00	232.25	181.00	45.25
Rockwool (medium density)	96.00	m ³	0.20		1137.00	227.4	121.80	24.36
Wall total						459.65		69.61
Ground:								
Reinforced concrete	2400.00	m ³	0.25		929.00	232.25	181.00	45.25
Foam glass	165.00	kg	0.10		21.48	354.42	1.45	23.925
Ground total						586.67		69.175
Roof:								
Reinforced concrete	2400.00	m ³	0.25		929.00	232.25	181.00	45.25
Rockwool (high density)	155.00	m ³	0.20		1836.00	367.2	196.60	39.32
Roof total						599.45		84.57

Figure 2 illustrates the geometric variants based on a cube of dimensions 3 m × 3 m × 3 m, which may be interpreted as a representation of a diminutive domestic dwelling (kind of tiny house). With the exception of variant A, all others are multiples of it in one, two, or all three axial directions. For each variant, the shape factor and the total PENRT and GWP values were calculated.

Figure 2. Geometric variants of the building under study based on a cube of dimensions $3\text{ m} \times 3\text{ m} \times 3\text{ m}$ (variant A). Letters A to I denote the single variants.

For the shape factor, F_b , the following relationship holds:

$$F_b = \Sigma A_i / V_b \quad (1)$$

where ΣA_i is the sum of the heat transfer areas of the building envelope, including the floor on the ground, and V_b is the building's heated volume (width \times length \times height).

The $PENRT_b$ value of the whole building has been calculated as:

$$PENRT_b = \sum A_{comp} \cdot PENRT_{comp} \quad (2)$$

where A_{comp} is the area of the relevant heat exchange component of the building envelope (wall, roof, floor, and windows) and $PENRT_{comp}$ is its PENRT value. The GWP_b of the whole building was calculated in the same way. The database of the German Federal Ministry for Living, Urban Development and Construction, Ökobaudat [26], which is freely available on the Internet, was used to obtain the PENRT and GWP values of the envelope components (for the sake of simplicity, only the values for categories A1 to A3 (production) were taken into account).

3. Results

A comparison of the variants studied in terms of their shape factor, the PENRT/GWP absolute value of the high-mass building, and the PENRT/GWP value related to 1 m^2 of the heated floor area is presented in Table 2. It shows that there is an inverse relationship between the shape factor and the absolute PENRT/GWP value, i.e., the lower the shape factor, the higher the absolute PENRT/GWP value (small buildings with fewer floors, i.e., higher shape factor, require less energy input in absolute terms than large buildings with a higher number of floors).

However, if we convert the PENRT/GWP values per m^2 of floor area of heated space, then there is direct proportionality between the $PENRT/\text{m}^2$ or GWP/m^2 values and the shape factor, i.e., more heated floors for the same building volume leads to more efficient use of embodied fossil fuel energy. Figure 3 presents a graph with the absolute PENRT values of the different variants in relation to the shape factor. Figure 4 is a graph with the PENRT values converted per 1 m^2 of heated area and related to the shape factor.

Table 2. Comparison of high-mass envelope variants studied in terms of their shape factor, F_b , and the respective PENRT/GWP value.

Variant	Shape Factor, F_b [m^{-1}]	PENRT [MJ]	PENRT/ m^2 [MJ/m^2]	GWP [kg CO ₂ -eq.]	GWP/ m^2 [kg CO ₂ -eq./ m^2]
A	2.00	38,047.88	4227.54	4335.79	481.75
B	1.67	62,409.36	3467.19	7195.53	399.75
C	1.56	86,770.84	3213.73	10,055.28	372.42
D	1.33	103,468.56	2874.13	11,623.65	322.88
G	1.11	196,262.04	2422.99	21,863.60	269.92
E	1.00	152,191.52	2113.77	17,343.14	240.88
F	0.89	200,914.48	1860.32	23,062.63	213.54
H	0.78	269,346.48	1662.63	30,442.83	187.92
I	0.67	342,430.92	1409.18	39,022.07	160.58

Figure 3. Comparison of high-mass envelope variants studied in terms of their shape factor, F_b , and the absolute PENRT value. The shape factor (line) is linked to the secondary y-axis and the absolute PENRT value to the primary y-axis.

Figure 4. Comparison of high-mass envelope variants studied in terms of their shape factor, F_b , and the PENRT value converted to $1 m^2$ of floor area of heated space. The shape factor (line) is linked to the secondary y-axis and the PENRT/ m^2 value to the primary y-axis.

The graphs in Figures 5 and 6 show the results in space to correspond with Figure 2. The figures highlight the contrast between the reduction in the shape factor and the increase in the absolute PENRT value of the building.

Figure 5. Illustration of the decrease in shape factor with an increasing number of stories, i.e., the increasing heated volume of the high-mass building relative to the surface of the building envelope.

Figure 6. Illustration of the increase in absolute PENRT value with increasing number of stories.

In the case of an unusual geometry that moves significantly away from a cube, as in the case of variant G, there may be some deviation from the trend. However, it is important to note that energy certification considers a range of shape factor values from approximately 0.3 to 1.0. This range corresponds to normal, realistic building shapes. Anything outside this range, i.e., with $F_b > 1.0$, is more of an outlier in the form of very small buildings.

The GWP values basically follow the PENRT values but on a different scale. Figure 7 presents a graph with the absolute GWP values of the variants studied in relation to the shape factor. Figure 8 is a graph with the GWP values converted per 1 m² of heated area and related to the shape factor.

The results described above were obtained for a building with a high-mass envelope. They justify the relevance of assessing the environmental indicators PENRT and GWP in relation to 1 m² of heated floor area and based on the building shape factor. It is clear from the graphs in Figures 3, 4, 7 and 8 that setting the criteria at the level of absolute values does not make sense as it favours smaller buildings and does not say much about the efficiency of the embodied energy and the greenhouse gas emissions generated.

Figure 7. Comparison of high-mass envelope variants studied in terms of their shape factor, F_b , and the absolute GWP value. The shape factor (line) is linked to the secondary y-axis and the absolute GWP value to the primary y-axis.

Figure 8. Comparison of high-mass envelope variants studied in terms of their shape factor, F_b , and the GWP value converted to 1 m² of floor area of heated space. The shape factor (line) is linked to the secondary y-axis and the GWP/m² value to the primary y-axis.

Of course, in addition to high-mass buildings, wood-based lightweight construction systems are also used, particularly in single-family homes and low-rise apartment blocks. It is highly probable that the PENRT and GWP values of these structures are considerably lower than those of high-mass buildings. This study provides evidence to support this hypothesis by using a building with a building envelope and geometries that are identical to the high-mass building previously described, with the exception that reinforced concrete has been replaced by timber in the walls and roof. The wood properties considered were raw density = 492.92 kg/m³, thickness = 0.05 m, thermal conductivity coefficient = 0.18 W/(mK), PENRT/unit = 485.6 MJ, and GWP/unit = −768.7 kg CO₂-equivalent. It was established that the thermal resistance of the wall and roof of both high-mass and lightweight buildings is approximately equivalent to 5.2 m²K/W. Leaving

aside the effect of thermal inertia, the heat flow through them is the same in both cases. The environmental indicators of a building with a lightweight envelope in relation to the shape factor are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison of lightweight envelope variants studied in terms of their shape factor, F_b , and the respective PENRT/GWP value.

Variant	Shape Factor, F_b [m^{-1}]	PENRT [MJ]	PENRT/ m^2 [MJ/ m^2]	GWP [kg CO ₂ -eq.]	GWP/ m^2 [kg CO ₂ -eq./ m^2]
A	2.00	17,172.15	1908.02	1381.74	153.53
B	1.67	30,159.90	1675.55	2387.88	132.66
C	1.56	43,147.65	1598.06	3394.02	125.70
D	1.33	42,713.10	1186.48	3514.68	97.63
G	1.11	76,622.85	945.96	5526.96	76.76
E	1.00	68,688.60	954.01	7539.24	69.81
F	0.89	94,664.10	876.52	6398.82	79.00
H	0.78	115,586.10	713.49	9417.24	58.13
I	0.67	154,549.35	636.01	12,435.66	51.18

A comparison of the PENRT/ m^2 and GWP/ m^2 values of the two building types is shown in the graphs in Figures 9 and 10. Evidently, once criteria for assessing embodied energy and GHG emissions are established, a distinction should be made between high-mass and lightweight construction in particular. The distinction according to the function of the building is not very meaningful in this respect.

Figure 9. Comparison of high-mass and lightweight envelope variants studied in terms of their shape factor, F_b , and the PENRT value converted to 1 m^2 of floor area of heated space. The shape factor (line) is linked to the secondary y-axis and the PENRT/ m^2 value to the primary y-axis.

Figure 10. Comparison of high-mass and lightweight envelope variants studied in terms of their shape factor, F_b , and the GWP value converted to 1 m² of floor area of heated space. The shape factor (line) is linked to the secondary y-axis and the GWP/m² value to the primary y-axis.

4. Discussion

At present, the concept of assessing heating demand based on the shape factor, which is otherwise enshrined in the standards of several EU countries, is receding significantly in the perception of the professional public. This is due to the NZEB legislation, which sets fixed single-number values for the different energy classes of buildings, regardless of their shape. The required single-number values roughly correspond to shape factor values of 0.7 and 0.8, respectively. More compact buildings can, therefore, afford higher average U-values and, therefore, more glazing. This may also have been the intention of the legislator, as the grading of the criteria according to the shape factor has led to the minimisation of windows to the smallest dimensions necessary for daylighting and solar gain in interiors.

The assessment of operational energy is a multifaceted process, encompassing various factors such as the evaluation of hygiene criteria, the impact of solar gains, building occupants, ventilation losses, etc. However, in environmental assessment, there is generally an assumption that the basic functionality of the elements (buildings, envelopes) in question has already been met [21]. The use of the shape factor in the assessment of environmental values is, therefore, directly on the hand. Nevertheless, the benchmark values should not be based on absolute values but in relation to the 1 m² of heated area of the building, which is what this study tried to show.

In contrast to energy certification, the development of the criteria for assessing the environmental performance of buildings is still at an early stage. The study by Gervasio, H. and Dimova, S. [16] for the European Commission acknowledges that it will be a process of gradual fine-tuning in terms of increasing complexity and refinement. As a first step, they propose to assess the environmental performance of the existing building stock and, on this basis, to establish appropriate indicators and criteria. The assessment should probably be carried out by the competent authorities of each EU Member State. In the opinion of the authors of this article, this will be a very administratively demanding task, which will also not be possible without a large number of assumptions, as it is rather difficult to obtain information about the embodied materials recursively.

Probably a more feasible way would be to develop criteria in cooperation with the construction community (developers, builders, designers). As energy certification assesses the quality of the building envelope from a thermo-technical point of view and also includes a building shape factor (in several countries), it might not be a significant challenge to request fundamental information on the PENRT and GWP values of the main components of the building envelope and their total sum per m^2 of heated floor area. On the basis of the data thus obtained, realistic values of PENRT/m^2 and GWP/m^2 of heated floor area could be established in relation to the shape factor. Subsequently, criteria for maximum values of PENRT/m^2 and GWP/m^2 could then be developed and graded in relation to the building shape factor. However, a distinction should be made between high-mass and lightweight construction at least, because the difference in the PENRT and GWP results is far too great.

5. Conclusions

Standardisation in the field of environmental assessment of buildings is at a relatively advanced stage, as evidenced by the set of ISO standards in the 14th series [14]. However, the selection and development of criteria is still at an early stage. PENRT and GWP would be appropriate criteria to consider as they are likely to be the most effective in reducing the use of fossil fuel energy and the resulting greenhouse gas emissions, thus slowing climate change. A number of studies mentioned in the paper use these criteria. Given the lack of data on embodied energy in buildings, the first step is to establish realistic values on which to base the structure and values of each benchmark. One possibility is the path outlined in the European Commission's 2018 JRC Technical Report [16], which foresees a detailed survey of the existing building stock. The disadvantage of this approach is not only the likely financial and administrative complexity but also the high level of uncertainty in the results, as information on embodied materials is relatively difficult to obtain retrospectively.

The second option described in this paper is to link PENRT and GWP assessment to the energy certification of buildings, thus involving the building community (developers, builders, designers) in the process of preparing and developing the criteria. As a first step, applicants for energy certificates for new buildings would only be required to calculate PENRT and GWP for the building envelope, the geometry of which they have to describe in detail anyway. In addition, they are required to calculate the building shape factor, which is also not a major problem. Based on a representative number of buildings described in this way, it would already be possible to establish benchmarks for the PENRT/m^2 (or GWP/m^2) of the heated area of the building in relation to its shape factor. There is a direct proportionality between these values, as shown by the results of the study presented in this paper. The next step is to find an appropriate function between the PENRT/m^2 (or GWP/m^2) and the shape factor that corresponds to the reality of the country and its ambitions. Relating the benchmarks for PENRT or GWP to the shape factor is a fairer way of assessing the quality of the building envelope than a single numerical value for any geometry, as it takes into account the efficiency of the use of embodied energy from non-renewable sources or the greenhouse gases emitted.

An unintended benefit of the second option of environmental assessment of buildings could also be that the time and administrative burden saved by the national authorities concerned could be redirected to the establishment and regular updating of databases of environmental indicators at the level of individual EU countries. High-quality databases of environmental indicators for materials and products are essential for a credible assessment of the environmental quality of buildings and its acceptance by the professional community as an additional, albeit administrative, but nevertheless well-intentioned obligation.

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References

1. European Commission. The European Green Deal. COM (2019) 640 final. In Proceedings of the Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, Brussels, Belgium, 11 December 2019.
2. European Commission. A Renovation Wave for Europe—Greening our Buildings, Creating Jobs, Improving Lives. COM/2020/662 final. In Proceedings of the Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, Brussels, Belgium, 14 October 2020.
3. Directive 2002/91/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2002 on the Energy Performance of Buildings. In *Official Journal of the European Communities*; European Union: Brussels, Belgium, 2002.
4. Directive 2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the Energy Performance of Buildings (Recast). In *Official Journal of the European Communities*; European Union: Brussels, Belgium, 2010.
5. Directive 2012/27/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on Energy Efficiency, Amending Directives 2009/125/EC and 2010/30/EU and Repealing Directives 2004/8/EC and 2006/32/EC (Audit). In *Official Journal of the European Communities*; European Union: Brussels, Belgium, 2012.
6. Directive 2018/844/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 Amending Directive 2010/31/EU on the Energy Performance of Buildings and Directive 2012/27/EU on Energy Efficiency. In *Official Journal of the European Communities*; European Union: Brussels, Belgium, 2018.
7. Directive (EU) 2024/1275 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 April 2024 on the Energy Performance of Buildings (Recast) (Text with EEA relevance). In *Official Journal of the European Communities*; European Union: Brussels, Belgium, 2024.
8. M343; Mandate of the European Commission to CEN, CENELEC and ETSI for the Elaboration and Adoption of Standards for a Methodology Calculating the Integrated Energy Performance of Buildings and Estimating the Environmental Impact, in Accordance with the Terms Set Forth in Directive 2002/91/EC, European Commission, Directorate-General for Energy and Transport, Directorate D—New Energies & Demand Management, Regulatory Policy & Promotion of New Energies and of Demand Management. European Commission: Brussels, Belgium, 2004.

9. M480; Mandate of the European Commission to CEN, CENELEC and ETSI for the Elaboration and Adoption of Standards for a Methodology Calculating the Integrated Energy Performance of Buildings and Promoting the Energy Efficiency of Buildings, in Accordance with the Terms Set in the Recast of the Directive on the Energy Performance of Buildings (Directive 2010/31/EU), European Commission, Directorate-General for Energy, Directorate C—New and renewable sources of energy, Energy Efficiency & Innovation, C.3—Energy Efficiency of Products & Intelligent Energy—Europe. European Commission: Brussels, Belgium, 2010.
10. Waltjen, T.; Mötzl, H.; Mück, W.; Torghelle, K.; Zelger, T. *Ökologischer Bauteilkatalog. Bewertete Gängige Konstruktionen*; (Catalogue of Ecological Components. Evaluated Common Constructions). IBO, Österr. Inst. f. Baubiologie u.-ökologie u. d. Zentrum f. Bauen u. Umwelt, Donau-Univ. Krems; Springer: Berlin, Germany, 1999. (In German)
11. BREEAM | Sustainable Building Certification. Available online: <https://breeam.com> (accessed on 8 December 2024).
12. LEED Rating System | U.S. Green Building Council. Available online: <https://www.usgbc.org/leed> (accessed on 8 December 2024).
13. German Sustainable Building Council | DGNB. Available online: <https://www.dgnb.de/en> (accessed on 8 December 2024).
14. ISO 14025:2006; Environmental Labels and Declarations—Type III Environmental Declarations—Principles and Procedures. International Organization for Standardization: Geneva, Switzerland, 2006.
15. Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2011 laying down harmonised conditions for the marketing of construction products and repealing Council Directive 89/106/EEC (Text with EEA relevance). In *Official Journal of the European Communities*; European Union: Brussels, Belgium, 2011.
16. Gervasio, H.; Dimova, S. *Environmental Benchmarks for Buildings*; EUR 29145 EN; JRC110085; Publications Office of the European Union: Luxembourg, 2018; ISBN 978-92-79-80970-5. [[CrossRef](#)]
17. Mahdavi, A.; Brahme, R.; Mathew, P. The “LEK”-Concept and its Applicability for the Energy Analysis of Commercial Buildings. *Build. Environ.* **1996**, *31*, 409–415. [[CrossRef](#)]
18. Heindl, W.; Grilli, P.V. *On Establishing Standards for the Overall Heat Transfer Coefficient of Buildings*; CIB-W67-Workshop: Vienna, Austria, 1991.
19. Uyttenbroeck, J. Thermal insulation and ventilation in buildings; a comparison of requirements in EEC-member States. In *CEC-Directorate General for Energy*; European Union: Brussels, Belgium, 1987.
20. Fantl, K.; Panzhauser, E.; Wunderer, E. *Der Österreichische Gebäude-Energieausweis. Energiepass*; The Austrian Building Energy Certificate. Energy Certificate; TU Wien: Vienna, Austria, 1996. (In German)
21. Pfundstein, M.; Gellert, R.; Spitzner, M.H.; Rudolphi, A. *Insulating Materials: Principles, Materials, Applications*, 1st ed.; Birkhäuserverlag—Edition Detail: Basel, Switzerland, 2008; pp. 93–105.
22. STN 73 0540; Thermal Protection of Buildings. Thermal Performance of Buildings and Components. Part 2: Functional Requirements. Slovak Office of Standards, Metrology and Testing: Bratislava, Slovakia, 2012. (In Slovak)
23. Verordnung über energiesparenden Wärmeschutz und energiesparende Anlagentechnik bei Gebäuden (Energieeinsparverordnung—EnEV) vom 16. November 2001 (Regulation on energy-saving thermal insulation and energy-saving technical systems for buildings (Energy Saving Regulation—EnEV) of 16 November 2001). In *Bundesgesetzblatt*; No. 59; Federal Ministry of Justice, Bundesanzeiger Verlag GmbH: Cologne, Germany, 2001. (In German)
24. Close, P.D. *Building Insulation*, 3rd ed.; American Technical Society: Chicago, IL, USA, 1946; pp. 205–225.
25. Rabenseifer, R.; Hraška, J.; Borovská, E.; Babenko, M.; Hanuliak, P.; Vacek, Š. Sustainable Building Policies in Central Europe: Insights and Future Perspectives. *Energies* **2022**, *15*, 1356. [[CrossRef](#)]
26. Ökobaudat. Available online: <https://www.oekobaudat.de> (accessed on 8 December 2024).

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